

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONFLICTOLOGY IN ENSURING NEIGHBORHOOD STABILITY

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Abstract: The article analyzes the role and importance of conflictology in ensuring neighborhood stability from a sociological perspective. The main purpose of the study is to study the conflict management mechanisms of the neighborhood institute from a theoretical and practical perspective. The author reveals the theoretical foundations of neighborhood stability based on the theories of functionalism and conflictological realism. The article classifies the types of conflicts (family-domestic, territorial-communal, social-resource and value conflicts) that occur in neighborhood communities and analyzes their causes. Special attention is paid to the conflict resolution mechanisms of the neighborhood institute (conciliation commissions, social mediation, preventive measures and legal and educational influence). The experience of conflict management in Uzbekistan's neighborhoods is considered as an "Uzbek model" in the international context. The results of the study show that the combination of traditional values and modern conflict management mechanisms is an effective way to ensure social stability.

Keywords: conflictology, neighborhood, social stability, mediation, social capital, conflict management.

ВАЖНОСТЬ КОНФЛИКТОЛОГИИ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ РАЙОНА

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Аннотация: В статье анализируется роль и значение конфликтологии в обеспечении стабильности махалли с социологической точки зрения. Основная цель исследования заключается в теоретическом и практическом изучении механизмов управления конфликтами институтом махалли. Автор раскрывает теоретические основы стабильности махалли на базе теорий функционализма и конфликтологического реализма. В статье классифицируются типы конфликтов, возникающих в махаллинских сообществах (семейно-бытовые, территориально-коммунальные, социально-ресурсные и конфликты ценностей), а также анализируются причины их возникновения. Особое внимание уделяется механизмам разрешения конфликтов институтом махалли (примирительные комиссии, социальная медиация, превентивные меры и правовое просвещение). Опыт управления конфликтами в махаллях Узбекистана рассматривается в международном контексте как "узбекская модель".

Результаты исследования показывают, что гармоничное сочетание традиционных ценностей и

современных механизмов управления конфликтами является эффективным путем обеспечения социальной стабильности.

Ключевые слова: конфликтология, махалля, социальная стабильность, медиация, социальный капитал, управление конфликтами.

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Annotation: The article analyzes the role and significance of conflictology in ensuring the stability of

mahalla from a sociological perspective. The main objective of the research is to theoretically

and practically study the conflict management mechanisms of the mahalla institution. The

author reveals the theoretical foundations of mahalla stability based on the theories of

functionalism and conflictological realism. The article classifies the types of conflicts occurring

in mahalla communities (family-domestic, territorial-communal, social-resource, and value

conflicts) and analyzes the causes of their emergence. Particular attention is paid to the

mechanisms of conflict resolution by the mahalla institution (reconciliation commissions, social mediation, preventive measures, and legal education). The experience of conflict management in Uzbekistan's mahallas is examined in an international context as the "Uzbek model." The research results demonstrate that the harmonious combination of traditional values and modern conflict management mechanisms is an effective path to ensuring social stability.

Key words: conflictology, mahalla, social stability, mediation, social capital, conflict management.

Enter 1. Conflictology and neighborhood stability: theoretical foundations. From the perspective of conflictology, the neighborhood is a microsystem of social relations, the stability of which is dynamic. Theoretically, it is possible to combine the views of two main schools of thought in ensuring neighborhood stability. First, from the point of view of functionalism (T. Parsons, R. Merton), the neighborhood is a key link in maintaining the balance of society, and each social conflict in it is seen as a threat to the overall functioning of the system. Accordingly, the task of the neighborhood institution is to maintain social integration and prevent disruptions in the system. On the other hand, the approach of conflictological realism (L. Kozler, R. Darendorf) considers conflicts to be a natural state in neighborhood life. According to L. Kozler's theory of "social conflict functions", open and controlled conflicts serve to renew old views in the neighborhood, restore social justice, and strengthen intergroup cohesion. That is, neighborhood stability does not mean the elimination of all conflicts, but the existence of mechanisms for their

transformation from a destructive (destructive) form to a constructive (creative) form.
The institution of the neighborhood

The concept of "social capital" is central to the theoretical model. According to the theories of J. Coleman and R. Putnam, the set of trust, mutual assistance, and common norms between members of a neighborhood is an immune system that prevents conflicts. If social capital is high in a neighborhood, institutionalized (conciliation commissions) and non-institutionalized (elders' advice, public opinion) mechanisms for resolving conflicts work effectively there. Therefore, the theoretical basis of neighborhood stability is the process of constantly restoring the balance between the personal interests of the individual and the general interests of the community (social agreement).

2. Types of conflicts that occur in neighborhood communities. Conflicts that affect neighborhood stability are diverse in their origin, subjects, and forms of manifestation. Based on sociological research and conflictological definitions, the main types of conflicts in mahalla communities can be grouped as follows. First, family and domestic disputes and conflicts. These types of conflicts are the most common and most complex areas of mahalla life. These include disputes between spouses on the verge of divorce, misunderstandings in mother-in-law-daughter-in-law relations, and social conflicts related to child rearing. Since the emotional connection between the subjects of these conflicts is strong, their resolution requires not only a legal, but also a deep psychological and spiritual approach. Second, territorial and communal-economic conflicts. Such conflicts are mainly manifested in neighborly relations. For example, disputes over land boundaries, public roads and canals, inconveniences of construction work, or public utilities (water, electricity, waste treatment) are among them. Such conflicts often arise as a result of a clash of material interests and directly undermine community cohesion. Third, social-resource conflicts. Today, the widespread assignment of social protection functions (assigning financial assistance, providing

subsidies, and providing preferential loans) to the mahalla institution has led to an increase in this type of conflict. The difference in the concepts of "fair distribution" among citizens can lead to vertical conflicts between mahalla activists and the population. In this case, lack of information or low transparency serves as the main factor provoking conflict. Fourth, conflicts of values and intergenerational conflicts. In the context of globalization, the differences between the traditional views of the older generation living in the neighborhood and the modern lifestyle and worldview of the young are creating social tension. These "cultural conflicts" are clearly visible in matters of etiquette, dress code, and social behavior. The study of these types of conflicts shows that each of them has a specific impact on the general social environment of the neighborhood. Timely identification of these conflicts is a key step in choosing the right strategy for their elimination.

3. Conflict resolution mechanisms of the mahalla institute. The mahalla institute acts as a kind of "multi-stage filter" in resolving disputes. Its mechanisms are both formal and informal-social in nature, and the effectiveness of this system allows us to stop conflicts at the pre-trial stage. Below we will systematically analyze these mechanisms. The first mechanism: Institutional approach (Reconciliation commissions). The "Reconciliation commission" under the mahalla citizens' assembly is the main institution for resolving disputes. Its activities are regulated by relevant secondary legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The commission includes the mahalla chairman, a women's activist, a prevention inspector, and reputable mahalla activists. The uniqueness of this mechanism is that face-to-face dialogue is held with the subjects of the dispute. The members of the commission are not only representatives of the parties. The second mechanism: Social mediation and public control. In conflictology, mediation is the art of reaching an agreement with the participation of an impartial third party. In the mahalla, this task is carried out by the "Council of Elders".

Their mechanism is based on the principle of "soft power". The spiritual authority and advice of the enlightened ones often have a stronger effect than legal sanctions. Also, social pressure is exerted on the conflicting parties through methods such as "Mahalla dakkisi" or public discussion. This mechanism is the most effective tool for preventing "facelessness", especially in household-neighborhood and family relations. The third mechanism: Preventive (warning) mechanism. The most important link in managing conflicts in the mahalla is to stop this conflict before it arises. This includes "household-based" monitoring and social prevention measures. For example, a women's activist works with troubled families, and a youth leader establishes a dialogue with unemployed youth to extinguish potential sources of conflict. In this process, a "Family Conflict Map" and Modern methods such as "social portrait" are being used. The fourth mechanism: Legal and educational impact. Many conflicts arise due to low legal literacy of citizens (for example, inheritance or land disputes). "Legal advocacy" events conducted by the neighborhood prevention inspector and involved lawyers show the legal solution to conflicts. This encourages the parties, who are given to emotions, to make legal and rational decisions. The integrated use of these mechanisms turns the neighborhood institution into the most solid shield ensuring social stability in society. Their effectiveness is that after the conflict is resolved, not hostility between the parties, but the possibility of continuing to live together (social reintegration) remains.

4. Experience in conflict management in mahallas of Uzbekistan. The process of modernization of the mahalla system in Uzbekistan has ensured the transition from traditional methods of conflict management to a systemic-institutional management model. Today, the experience accumulated in our country's mahallas is recognized not only regionally, but also internationally as a unique "Uzbek model". The introduction of the "mahalla seven" system. The most important of the latest experiences is the involvement of professional specialists in mahalla management. Previously, only the

mahalla chairman and advisors dealt with conflicts, but now, within the framework of the "mahallabay" work system, a representative of each sector is determined to be responsible for a specific factor in the conflict. For example, the economic causes of family conflicts are resolved by the assistant khokim (through employment and credit), the legal aspects are resolved by the prevention inspector, and the spiritual and psychological aspects are resolved by a women's activist. This experience ensures that conflict resolution is professional and targeted. Integration of professional mediation services. An important innovation of the Uzbek experience is the establishment of cooperation with professional mediators and lawyers in makhallas. After the adoption of the Law "On Mediation", special "Mediation Rooms" were established in many makhalla buildings. According to the Ministry of Justice, thousands of family divorces are prevented annually through the efforts of conciliation commissions and mediators in makhallas, and tens of thousands of civil disputes are resolved at the pre-trial stage. This reduces the workload of judicial bodies and serves to increase legal culture in society. Digitalization and the experience of "Social Service". In modern experience, the use of digital technologies in conflict management (for example, the "Online Mahalla" platform) has been established. Through this system, information on the level of social tension in the makhalla, low-income families, and persons on preventive accounts is centralized. The assignment of employees of the "Inson" social service centers to neighborhoods has created the opportunity to provide professional psychological and social assistance to individuals in conflict situations. International comparison and effectiveness. The experience of Uzbekistan shows that the most effective method of managing conflicts in the neighborhood is the "prevention - dialogue - reconciliation" chain. For example, in 2023 The fact that over 80 percent of family disputes considered by the reconciliation commissions in the mahallas throughout the republic were resolved positively proves the viability of this institution. Also, the reduction in unemployment

through the mahalla system of work leads to an improvement in the criminal situation in the regions and a natural decrease in social conflicts. In conclusion, Uzbekistan's experience in managing conflicts at the mahalla level remains one of the most important social drivers ensuring the sustainable development of society. This experience is significant in that it combines ancient values and modern management methods.

Conclusion and suggestions

Based on the theoretical and practical analyses described above, the following conclusions can be drawn. First, the science of conflictology is of great theoretical and practical importance in ensuring the stability of the mahalla. Functional conflict theory and the concept of social capital allow us to understand the mechanisms for transforming conflicts in the mahalla into a constructive direction. The stability of the mahalla is not the absence of conflicts, but the ability to systematically manage them. Secondly, the conflicts that occur in mahalla communities (family-domestic, territorial-communal, social-resource and value conflicts) have their own characteristics, each of which requires a separate approach. Timely identification of these conflicts and choosing the right strategy are the main conditions for the stability of the mahalla.

Third, the multi-stage system of conflict management in Uzbekistan's makhallas (conciliation commissions, social mediation, preventive mechanisms and legal and educational impact) has proven its effectiveness. The "makhalla-based" system, professional mediation services and digitalization processes have replaced traditional mechanisms with modern management

Fourth, the role of the mahalla institution in conflict management is a key factor in ensuring social stability not only at the local but also at the national level. The fact that more than 80 percent of disputes resolved at the mahalla level are resolved positively at the pre-trial stage reduces the workload of the judicial system and strengthens social harmony in society.

Offers:

1. It is necessary to introduce a system of special training and retraining courses in order to increase the conflictological competencies of mahalla employees. This should include not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical mediation and negotiation skills. 2.

Creating the possibility of eliminating potential conflict sources in advance by introducing "Early Conflict Detection Monitoring" in mahallas. For this, it is advisable to use digital platforms and social media monitoring systems. 3. The burden on the judicial system can be reduced by further developing the Institute of Social Mediation and increasing the number of certified mediators at the mahalla level. 4. It is necessary to create a platform for practical experience for students in conflictology, sociology and psychology and to activate research work by expanding mahalla-higher educational institutions cooperation. 5. Conflicts of values can be prevented by strengthening spiritual and educational work in neighborhoods and building bridges of communication between different generations. In conclusion, it is worth noting that the importance of conflictology in ensuring neighborhood stability is increasing day by day. The experience of Uzbekistan shows that the combination of traditional values and modern conflict management mechanisms is the most effective way to ensure social stability.

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